

Collaborative Engagement Between Stakeholders in Enhancing Successful Identification of Learners with Barriers

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Abstract:- The purpose of this manuscript is to outline the collaborative engagement between stakeholders in enhancing successful identification of LSEN. This article reports on a study that focused on the collaboration and engagement of different stakeholders in identifying learners with learning barriers. The purpose of the study was to explore stakeholder's engagement in identifying learners with learning barriers with the intention of positive intervention provision. The second purpose is to enhance the implementation of (SIAS) policy in identifying learners with learning barriers.

The set objectives for the study was to explore collaborative engagement between stakeholders in enhancing successful implementation of (SIAS) in identifying learners with learning barriers. A qualitative research approach was followed, underpinned by interpretive method as a paradigm. Participants were purposefully selected. Data were collected through semi-structured interviews. The participants included were from three inclusive schools.

Keywords:- Collaboration, Inclusive Education, Disability, Inclusion, Special Education Needs.

I. INTRODUCTION

The working together in a mutual manner in enhancing successful identification of learners with learning barriers always results in the achieving of the main goal hence the African idiom "It takes a village to raise a child," is an ancient African proverb. It means all the parents in a village would be honoured to take a role in helping to raise the child of a parent that might otherwise be busy with work or other chores that keep the parent away from parental duties. With all the mothers in the community keeping a watchful eye over the youth of the village, they would all benefit from the healthy nurturing of the children which they had a hand in helping to raise.

The research has shown in several ways that absence of collaborative engagement by stakeholders including parents, governmental and non-governmental organisation plays major role in the implementation of successful inclusive education. Collaboration entails the working together of all

stakeholders which will results in successful identification of learners with learning barriers.

To have proper functionality between all stakeholders the school needs to build harmonious relationship between all stakeholders responsible for the identification of learners with learning barriers. Parents are very pivotal stakeholders as well as teachers as they are parents in absence of biological parents i.e. *in locoparentis* meaning that teachers as parents must act and participate in a manner that it is in the interest of learners, (Wood, & Su, 2019).

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

The identification of learners with learning barriers has been a matter of interest for South African schools. This study sought to explore collaboration between stakeholders in ensuring successful inclusion of learners with learning barriers. For the prevalence of successful inclusion of learners with learning barriers, collaboration is essential.

Recent research (Samantha & Somerton (2023) concurred that collaborative partnership among stakeholders is vital to the education of every learners enrolled in inclusive schools. The national policy framework for teacher's education and development (NPFTED) affirms that the engagement between teachers and other members of learners support network, the extend of data examining stakeholders experiences in fulfilling these obligations remain unknown.

➤ *The aim of the study*

The study intends to explore the collaboration engagement of different stakeholders in identification of learners with learning barriers

➤ *Population sampling selection of participants*

The population of the study was made up of secondary school teachers in Matlosana local education office. Participants includes learners from secondary schools and primary schools in Matlosana local education office. Teachers from schools inter alia, both primary and secondary schools will be interviewed. Members from school based support team (SBST) from each selected schools will form part of the interviews.

III. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Qualitative research methodology is a broad approach to the study of a social phenomenon. A quantitative approach (Hayashi, Abib & Hoppens, 2019) is a formal, objective and systematic way of collecting numerical data and this enables the researcher to look for a relationship between the variables. The qualitative study method was deemed relevant because the purpose of the study is to outline collaboration of stakeholders in enhancing identification of learners with learning barriers. The qualitative method was also found to be more suitable because it deals with more subjective data that are produced by the minds of the participants during interviews.

➤ *Benefits of effective collaborative engagement*

Literature reveals that positive collaboration results in successful identification of learners with learning barriers. Positive engagement of all stakeholders encourage motivation thus may result in positive academic learner performance. Positive collaboration encourage and boost confidence and self-esteem as well, thus create better learning experience where learner identified with learning barriers may learn and achieve maximally the same as those who are said to be without barriers. Research shows that effective collaborative partnerships in education lead to greater teacher retention and educator empowerment, more effective communication among stakeholders, and an increase in student success, even in high poverty school districts.

➤ *Barriers to effective collaborative engagement*

In contrary to the benefits for effective collaboration there are barriers that hinders positive collaboration to identify learners with learning barriers. Lack of parental involvement has been seen as the most barrier that curb learner's achievement in many schools. Several researchers have proofed that lack of parental involvement in identifying learners with learning barriers has been a challenge for many years ago, thus hinders successful identification of learners with learning barriers.

Educators in schools serving disadvantaged communities are more likely to have a negative perception of parental involvement; often classifying it as less encouraging and less rewarding in terms of advancing children's learning (Koutrouba, Antonopoulou, Tsitsas & Zenakou, 2009; Luxomo & Motala, 2012; McDowall & Schaughency, 2017)

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Parents and school community usually report lack of time as the most important communication barrier. However, studies revealed that lack of planning towards establishment of cooperation and lack of developing mutual understanding are the most important communication barrier. Also, lack of technology can limit communication opportunities. The new technologies that provide convenience, efficiency, and effectiveness in knowledge transfer have an important force in the development of parent-teacher communication (Zieger & Tan, 2012).

➤ *Methodology and data collection*

The researcher adopted qualitative approach (Creswell, 2016; Maree, 2016) to explore the collaboration between the stakeholders in enhancing successful inclusion of learners with learning barriers. Data were generated through semi structured interviews, field notes, and transcripts of audio recording, and document analysis, largely of words or texts obtained from the participants while exploring the focus of the study.

The researcher in a qualitative approach will typically generate data at the site where participants experience the phenomenon under study. In following this approach, the researcher will enter the environment where the participants live or work, and obtain sufficient information before providing an account or reporting on the participants' experiences. When conducting semi-structured interviews allowed the researcher will collect direct information about the collaborative engagement between stakeholders in enhancing successful identification of learners with learning barriers.

IV. CONCLUSION

The aim of the study is to investigate and explore the collaboration engagement and participation of stakeholders in the identification of learners with learning barriers in inclusive schools. The study found that positive engagement of different stakeholder's results in many cases to the positive results in identifying learners with learning barriers. The data collection was done in Matlosana local education office in inclusive schools to explore collaboration of stakeholder's in identifying learners with learning barriers with the intention to provide necessary support so that they may also achieve maximally like those who are said to be without learning barriers.

Research has shown that positive collaboration has clear benefits for both learners and teachers. It was more evident that the positive collaboration engagement between stakeholders in enhancing successful identification of learners with learning barriers has positive end-results.

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